

Bringing the Value Back to Education

Dr. Antony D. Miller from Skyline University explores the evolution of technology and basic disciplines in education and how this has affected the ability of students across the world.

Is it still a teacher's duty to nurture the next generation so that it goes on to move our civilisation forward, or are they now being restricted in this duty by diluted standards compared to the 1980s, and unhelpful involvement of institutional stakeholders and parent governors in academic affairs?

For example, an institution that uses advanced technology may be more attractive for students and parents for a number of reasons. However, could technology also be diminishing students' basic mental skills, such as arithmetic and spelling, instead of simply providing a reference source and drafting method? In short, I have observed that students today are far removed from basic academic mental knowledge and its application compared to their predecessors a generation ago.

This erosion of school discipline could be endangering the future generation inter-socially. This is largely because since the late 1980s, educational institutions have become commercial, with the students now being customers for non-academic entities.

As a result, some students' mental or self-reasoning skills in problem-solving are being impaired. I believe that in another generation's time—from 2030 and beyond—graduates will be solely dependent on the IT gadgets at their disposal to acquire basic data instead of being able to use their own brain power.

The dangers of such devolution in our civilization are evident: both the increase in crime social-demographically and the financial crash are just a couple of factors. There is also the question of whether paying for your education could be a guarantee of graduating or passing a subject? To prevent this situation continuing, I believe that change should be implemented as soon as possible, and be initiated from primary school levels upward, inclusive of a child's monitoring program, which could continue until secondary school graduation.

Developing nations take credence from the western states; they have in fact replicated the models of developed countries to tweak their own respective educational institutions. In my view, if a change in legislation is not implemented by 2020, both our children's and grandchildren's educational futures may be non-complimentary.

Dr. Antony D. Miller from Skyline University

There should be harmony between academia and business to support education and the student body. This would bring about balance and make both the quality of student tuition and profitability the main achievements. There is a need for business collaboration and efficient teaching in an institution, and this ought to be a priority at this moment in time. I agree that we need business management investor influences and philanthropic donations, and a harmonious relationship could embrace both the business and academic worlds.

The result of deteriorating standards has seen graduates not being taken seriously by employers because of poor social and literacy skills. Some top companies in Europe and the U.S. use psychometric testing before a first interview to evaluate a candidate's personality type and behavioural style, as well as looking at their mental and social skills. I think similar monitoring in primary and secondary education could be very beneficial.

Overall, it is my view that the philosophy or mantra for education as a whole should be simple: institutions should not sell education itself to students and parents alike, but instead place more value on what the students can do with that education for themselves in the end.